

ionic radius or the atomic weight of the elements. But the total water content and the first endothermic peak temperature (DTA) were found to follow an inverse relationship with the ionic radius of the respective cations.

References

1. G. H. WHITING and W. E. S. TURNER, *J. Soc. Glass Technol.*, 1930, **14**, 409.
2. C. O. FURNAS, *Ind Eng Chem*, 1931, **23**, 534.
3. P. MURRAY and J. WHITE, *Trans. Brt. Ceram. Soc.*, 1955, **54**, 151.
4. W. E. GARNER and M. G. TANNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 47.
5. V. P. CHALYI, O. I. SHOR and S. P. ROZHENKO, *Ukr. Khim Zh*, 1961, **27**, 3.
6. N. F. ERMOLENKO, M. D. EYROS and L. I. IVASHKO, *Zh. Neorg. Khim*, 1966, **11**, 1569.
7. A. F. WELLS, "Structural Inorganic Chemistry", Clarendon, London, 1950, p. 416.

Syntheses of Hydroxytriazenes

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BAMBERGER¹, Gebhard and Thompson² were the first to synthesis hydroxytriazenes. The complexing ability of these compounds has been

examined by Elkins and Hunter³. The analytical uses of these compounds have been evaluated for the first time by Sogani and Bhattacharya⁴. Sogani *et al.*⁵⁻¹⁰ prepared a large number of these compounds and explored their utilities in analytical chemistry. Taking into consideration the increasing importance of hydroxytriazenes as chelating agents in analytical chemistry, ten new hydroxytriazenes have been synthesised.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligands: Isopropylhydroxylamine solution was prepared by reducing isonitropropane (25.0 ml) with zinc dust (30.0 g) in presence of NH₄Cl (30.0 g) at 0–15°. It was coupled at 0±2° with benzene diazonium chloride prepared from aniline (18.6 g). Sodium acetate solution (30%) was added occasionally. The granular yellow product was filtered off and crystallised twice from ethanol—water mixture to give light yellow crystals of 3-hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene (9.0g). Other ligands were prepared similarly by coupling isopropylhydroxylamine with the corresponding substituted benzene diazonium chloride. Elemental analysis and physical characteristics of the ligands thus prepared are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Compd.	Mol. formula	M.p. ^a °C	Colour	Analy-is : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	111 ^a	Light yellow	60.19 (60.34)	7.37 (7.26)	22.69 (23.46)
2.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-tolytriazene	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	133 ^a	Light violet	61.80 (62.17)	7.84 (7.77)	21.50 (21.76)
3.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl 1-p-chlorophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ OCl	191 ^a	Violet	51.04 (50.58)	6.00 (5.62)	19.65 (19.67)
4.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-bromophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ OBr	114 ^b	Light yellow	41.29 (41.86)	4.68 (4.65)	16.63 (16.27)
5.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-methoxyphenyltriazene	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	110 ^b	Light brown	57.61 (57.41)	7.38 (7.17)	20.24 (20.09)
6.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-carboxyphenyltriazene	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃	180 ^a	Light cream	53.66 (53.81)	6.03 (5.82)	18.6 (18.83)
7.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-m-acetylphenyltriazene	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	118 ^b	Light brown	59.89 (59.72)	6.88 (6.78)	18.46 (19.00)
8.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-nitrophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	125 ^b	Shining dark brown	48.82 (48.21)	5.42 (5.35)	24.82 (25.00)
9.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-m-nitrophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	157 ^a	Shining light yellow	48.82 (48.21)	5.42 (5.35)	24.82 (25.00)
10.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-o-nitrophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	82 ^b	Golden yellow	48.82 (48.21)	5.42 (5.35)	24.82 (25.00)

* Crystallised from : ^a ethanol-water, ^b ethanol.

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References

1. E. BAMBERGER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 104, 1897, **30**, 2280, 1897, **30**, 2285, 1900, **33**, 3510.
2. N. L. GEBHARD and H. B. THOMPSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 767.
3. M. ELKINS and L. HUNTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1346.
4. N. C. SOGANI and S. O. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 563.
5. N. C. SOGANI and S. O. BHATTACHARYA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 81.
6. H. K. L. GUPTA, T. O. JAIN and N. C. SOGANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 531.
7. H. K. L. GUPTA and N. C. SOGANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 771.
8. D. N. PUROHIT, S. M. DUGAR and N. C. SOGANI, unpublished.
9. D. N. PUROHIT, S. M. DUGAR and N. C. SOGANI, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1965, **20**, 853.
10. S. M. DUGAR and N. C. SOGANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **43**, 289.

Chemical Investigation of *Acrostichum aureum* Linn.

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ACROSTICHUM aureum (Adiantaceae), a tall, handsome, very tough fern native of North Nigeria, is also found in mangroves and marshy places in India¹. The plant is widely used as an indigenous drug in various ailments in Nigeria. The rhizome is pounded and grated and is applied as a paste to wounds and boils in Borneo and Malaya¹. Since no work seems to have been done on this medicinally important plant, it was subjected to extensive chemical investigation. The plant was procured from North Nigeria.

Experimental

The powdered plant material was exhaustively extracted with boiling ethanol (95%) and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The concentrated extract was fractionated into (i) light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) and (ii) ethyl acetate fractions. The petrol fraction was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. Elution of the column with different solvents and their mixtures yielded five fractions marked A, B, C, D and E. The ethyl acetate

soluble fraction on usual chromatographic resolution over silica gel furnished the products D, F, G and H.

Compound-A: It had m.p. 62–67°; glc analysis showed it to be a mixture of n-alkanes containing hentriacontane (36.3%), tritriacontane (28.9%), nonacosane (21.2%), triacantane (2.9%), heptacosane (2.0%), hexatriacontane (2.0%), octacosane (2.0%) accompanied by hexacosane, pentacosane and pentatriacontane as minor constituents.

Compound-B: On crystallisation (MeOH—CHCl₃) it furnished silky needles, m.p. 214–15°; identified as lupeol by m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with an authentic sample².

Compound-C: It was identified as Friedelin³, m.p. 259–60°; the oxime, colourless plates, m.p. 292–94°.

Compound-D: On crystallisation (CHCl₃—MeOH) it gave needles, m.p. 136–37°; the acetate, m.p. 125–26°; the benzoate, m.p. 142–43°; identification of the compound as β -sitosterol made through m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc, and preparation of derivatives.

Compound-E: It had m.p. 140–42°; gave positive Libermann—Burchard and tetranitromethane test; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 450 and 1 055 (OH), 1 640 (C=C), 1 460 and 1 381 cm⁻¹ (C—CH₃); the acetate, m.p. 127–30°; the benzoate, m.p. 145–48°. The gc-ms analysis of the product (TMS derivatives) showed it to be a mixture of campesterol (3%) (M^+ 473), stigmasterol (4%) (M^+ 484) and β -sitosterol (70.3%) (M^+ 486) in major amounts along with a few minor sterol isomers. It had a significant molecular ion peak M^+ 458 (may be cholesterol; 0.2%).

Fraction-F: It had m.p. 87° (Me₂CO) C₂₄H₄₈O₂ (M^+ 368); the methyl ester, m.p. 58–59°, identified as tetracosanoic acid⁴.

Compound G: It crystallised as shining needles, m.p. 284–86°; the acetate (CH₃COCH₃), colourless needles, m.p. 290–91°; the methyl ester (diazomethane) and methyl ester acetate, m.p. 172–73° and 243–45°, respectively. It was identified as ursolic acid⁵ by m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc, ir and preparation of derivatives.

Compound-H: It had m.p. 253°d, identified as gallic acid⁷ through m.p., m.m.p. and co-tlc with an authentic sample.

The defatted product was treated successively with water and aqueous NaOH (0.2%). After usual workup the residue was dissolved in absolute ethanol and applied on Whatman filter paper (no. 1)^{8,9}, developed with n-butanol—acetic acid—water (4:1:1, v/v). The chromatogram was sprayed with ninhydrin in acetone (0.1%), and finally dried in an electric oven at 55°. Amino acids were located as coloured spots. The observed R_f values of the various protein amino acids and those of authentic specimens agree fairly well with one another: R_f ($\times 100$) for methionine, 40.1, violet;